

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

COLD TOLERANCE

Agronomic traits of cold-tolerant rices

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In 1984, we evaluated 90 transplanted rice varieties for cold tolerance at Upper Shillong Farm (elevation 1900 m). Temperatures were low from panicle initiation through harvest. Entries included local and improved indicas and japonicas.

Maximum and minimum values for agronomic traits are in the table. K 332 had minimum days to 50% flowering; Namyi for minimum flag leaf angle; and Chhanapaddy for minimum grain sterility. The three are indica varieties.

There were significant positive relationships between grain yield and plant height (0.477), effective tillers per plant (0.321), flag leaf angle (0.387), grains per panicle (0.726), and harvest index (0.602). Percent sterility and grain yield were significantly and negatively

Agronomic traits of cold-tolerant rices, Shillong, India.

Character	Range		Mean	Correlation coefficient with grain yield ^a
	Minimum	Maximum		
Days to 50% flowering	121 (K332)	170 (Khamang, Kba-saw rit B ₂ & B ₄)	159.31	0.224
Plant height (cm)	60 (K332)	110 (Zichum)	88.77	0.477**
Leaf area index	1.84 (Ryllo red)	6.70 (PK2-26-1)	3.27	0.143
Tillers per plant	4 (Kba-sawrit B ₄)	16 (PK2-26-1)	7.91	0.207
Effective tillers per plant	4 (Kba-saw rit B ₄)	16 (PK2-26-1)	7.38	0.321*
Flag leaf angle (°)	70 (Namyi)	115 (PK2-3-1)	63.27	0.387**
Panicle length (cm)	15 (K-333)	24 (Dullo-8, CH-1039)	20.73	0.238
Grains per panicle	2.3 (Muzudo)	84.4 (Ryllo red A)	42.61	0.726**
Sterility (%)	27 (Chhanapaddy)	98 (Muzudo)	52.30	-0.594**
Harvest index	0.01 (Borkat)	0.70 (Ryllo red 6)	0.35	0.602**
Grain yield (t/ha)	(1.0 (Borkat)	2.5 (PK2-26-1)	0.91	

^aSignificant at 1% (**) and 5% (*) levels

related (-0.594).

PK2-26-1, Ryllo red A, and Namyi

may be suitable donors for cold tolerance breeding programs. *ℓ*

Cold tolerance of Yunnan rices at different elevations

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We tested 105 rice varieties from Yunnan Province for cold tolerance at early seedling, seedling, booting, and flowering stages at the Institute of Crop Germplasm Resources, Beijing.

Hei-Gu, Wu-Chew-Ma-Xian-Gu, Hong-Mang-Da-Ding, and Bi-Jing no. 7 had greatest cold tolerance at all stages. Bi-Gu, Lao-Lai-Hong, Bang-Tou-Nuo, Xiao-Ai-Jiao-Nuo, Da-Bai-Gu, Ziao-Hoang-Gu, Huang-La-Gu, Shi-Li-Xiang, Hai-Gu, Jiu-Gu, Han-Gu, Yu-Gu, and Lao-Lai-Bai had cold tolerance at flowering.

Correlation between cold tolerance and elevation at which rice varieties are planted.

Cold tolerance at early seedling, seedling, and flowering stages were

highly and significantly correlated with the elevation at which they were planted.

Correlation coefficients were 0.456**, 0.399**, and 0.527**.

Average cold tolerance of varieties was calculated for several growth stages: $S = s_1 + s_2 + s_3 + \dots s_n/n$. There was a highly significant correlation between

average score and elevation (see figure). Japonicas tend to have cold tolerance above 1,500 m elevation, indicas below 1,000 m, and japonica/indica between 1,000 and 1,500 m.

Agronomic characteristics also change with elevation. Lemma, palea, and apiculus colors are more intense and flag leaves shorter with increasing elevation. *ℒ*

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DEEP WATER

Selecting deep water rices with ratooning ability

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Cropping intensity in deep water rice areas is low because long-duration, photoperiod-sensitive varieties are needed. Boro or winter rice often is harvested too late to allow proper establishment of deep water rice. Photoperiod-sensitive rices with good ratooning ability, submergence tolerance, and elongation ability have potential as a dry season crop and as a deep water ratoon.

We evaluated 118 entries for ratooning ability in an unreplicated trial in Nov 1982-May 1983 at IRRI (see figure). At maturity, plants were cut to 15-cm height and 15 d later were scored for ratooning ability. Of the selections, 109 were evaluated in 1983 wet season and 1983-84 dry season to confirm their performance and ascertain the photoperiod sensitivity of the ratoons.

In the Nov 1982 planting, main crop flowering, maturity, and height varied substantially, perhaps because they were first planted at IRRI in dry season and have not been selected for uniformity. Within a variety, many hills did not produce ratoon tillers. Several plants, however, had good ratooning ability, which was based on high tiller number (≥ 16), at least 3 leaves per tiller before flowering, and freedom from virus diseases. Some entries flowered immediately after ratooning, others remained vegetative, and a few showed segregation for flowering. We selected entries that flowered soon after

Selection of deep water rices with ratooning ability, IRRI, 1982-84

ratooning and those that flowered late.

Early flowering ratoons were evaluated in Jun-Dec 1983. The main crop lodged seriously, and the ratoon crop had generally poor regeneration (0-

10%). Only Raj Bhawalia (Acc. 26517A) had relatively high regeneration. We attributed the poor ratooning to lodging during early growth.

Ratoons with delayed flowering were